

New Ways of Marketing Wool Profitable Use of wool

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Lojeño sheep during shearing at the farm of Juan Antonio Moreno Cobo, Loja, Granada

The removal of wool from livestock has shifted from being a significant source of income for the farm to becoming an added cost due to the complexity of its handling and its low price. Not all sheep breeds produce the same quality of wool, but all types are useful for various applications. It is essential to understand the variability of products that can be made from wool and to allocate it, according to the breed, to the most suitable product.

To achieve this, it is necessary to care for the wool to obtain high quality, making it more usable. In the case of *Lojeño* sheep, the wool comes from animals raised in agroforestry ecosystems, feeding in olive groves and *Mediterranean* forests, which reinforces the sustainable and ecological character of the product.

The Association of the *Lojeño* Sheep Breed has found innovative and sustainable uses for the wool produced by their livestock. They collaborate with some charitable organizations, such as the *Iaia* Association, where different wool pieces are made for social purposes. They also work with *Wooldreamer*, a family business that has chosen to revalue wool and its crafts. *Wooldreamer* handles the washing, processing, and spinning of the wool and sells products made from wool and skeins of wool from different sheep breeds in *Spain*. This way, they manage to sell certified yarns with 100% traceability.

The most notable innovation involves using wool waste, which is shredded and pelletized to create natural, organic, and ecological fertilizer for gardening, horticulture, greenhouses, and indoor plants. This fertilizer is produced in pellet form, is very rich in nitrogen, and has a slow release, taking several months to decompose. These pellets can retain up to four times their weight in water, making them very useful for sandy soils. These organic pellets are being sold in small sizes locally.

This new use of wool revalues a resource from an agroforestry system, bringing diversity and stability to this business model.

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